

Lagrangian Formalism, Special Relativity and Electromagnetism

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The Lagrangian formalism is often seen as a mathematical (variational calculus) approach to writing Newton's second law of motion. We try to argue, however, that it may be closely linked to special relativity by examining the case of a fixed charge Q at rest interacting with a test charge q along y as seen from a frame moving with a constant $-v$ (velocity). Given that there is an interaction energy $q\phi$ in the rest frame, it behaves like rest mass and should transform into a momentum. This momentum should appear in a d/dt momentum = some forces ((1)) equation, but the Lagrangian formalism goes beyond this because it sets some forces = $-dL/dx_i$ where L is the Lagrangian. The form $d/dt A = dA/dt$ partial + $v \cdot \text{grad} A$, We show that dA/dt partial is linked to special relativity. $v \cdot \text{grad} A$ on the other hand is one type of arrangement of v , $\text{grad} A$, but $-\text{grad}(v \cdot A)$ is another just as legitimate. We thus argue that a term $v \cdot A$ may be used in two ways. First, one may take $-\text{grad}(v \cdot A)$ to obtain a piece of force and then one may pull out A using $d/dv v \cdot A$ and then take d/dt full of this expression. We argue that this is one way to give rise to the notion of the Lagrangian approach.

In general, one uses the Lagrangian $L = .5mv \cdot v + q/c A \cdot v + q\phi$ and may show that it is consistent with a Lorentz force $F = qE + qv \times B$ where $B = \text{grad} \times A$ and $E = -\text{grad} \phi - dA/dt$ partial. Seen in this way, one does not notice the role of special relativity. In this note, we consider a charge Q at rest as seen by a moving frame ($-v$) in order to see how strongly connected the Lagrangian is with special relativity.

Lagrangian Formalism

The Lagrangian formalism defines a function $L(x, dx/dt, t)$ such that the functional calculus variation of:

Functional Variation $\int dt L = 0$ ((2))

This leads to the equation: $d/dt dL/dv_i - dL/dx_i = 0$ ((3)) for no constraints

(If constraints exist, they may be added using Lagrange multipliers.). The form $d/dt dL/dv_i$ is obtained using integration by parts. One may notice that ((3)) is of the form of Newton's second law if:

$dL/dv_i = \text{momentum (i)}$ and $dL/dx_i = \text{force}$ ((4))

For a simple problem with a conservative force $F = -\text{grad} V(x)$, one may use $L = .5mv^2 - V(x)$ as the Lagrangian.

At first sight, this has nothing to do with special relativity.

Electromagnetic Case

Consider the usual electromagnetic case for which there is an electrostatic potential $\phi(x_i, t)$ and magnetic vector potential A . The goal is to find a Lagrangian L such that ((3)) holds. In such a case, nonrelativistic for the particle, one wants:

$$m \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = \text{Lorentz force} = q\mathbf{E} + q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} \quad ((5))$$

One may show that: $L = \frac{1}{2} m \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v} + q/c \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v} - q\phi$ ((6)) in such a case, where:

$$\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{d\mathbf{A}}{dt} \text{ partial and } \mathbf{B} = \text{grad } \times \mathbf{A} \quad ((7a))$$

Here it is assumed that ϕ and A are not functions of \mathbf{v} , but of \mathbf{x}, t only. ((7b))

$$\left\{ \frac{d}{dt} (m\mathbf{v}_i + q/c A_i) - q \frac{d\phi}{dx_i} - q/c \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{d\mathbf{A}}{dx_i} = 0 \right.$$

Now: $\frac{d}{dt} A_i = \frac{dA_i}{dt} \text{ partial} + v_j \text{ dot } \frac{d}{dx_j} A_i$. Thus, one must show that: $v_j \frac{d}{dx_j} A_i - v_j \frac{dA_j}{dx_i}$

Is the same as: $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} = \epsilon_{ijk} v_j \epsilon_{klm} \frac{d}{dl} A_m = v_j \frac{d}{di} A_j - v_j \frac{d}{dj} A_i$

Thus, the Lagrangian ((6)) "works". We ask the question: Is there a way to see a connection of the Lagrangian with special relativity? To do so, we consider a charge Q at rest.

Charge Q at Rest as Seen from a Frame Moving with Constant $(\mathbf{v}_x, 0, 0)$ = velocity

In order to see special relativity at work, we consider a Lorentz transformation of the potential energy $q\phi$, where ϕ is the electrostatic potential from a charge Q at rest acting on a test charge q , held in place. This potential energy should transform as rest mass giving rise to a momentum. We call ϕ the potential as seen in the moving frame and A vector, its momentum.

$$\begin{aligned} |A| &= |g v g| |0| \quad ((8)) \quad g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \\ |\phi| &= |-g v g| |\phi''| \end{aligned}$$

Thus: $\phi = g \phi''$ and $A = v g \phi''$ ((9))

ϕ'' is a function of \mathbf{x}'' and t'' and so one wishes to use the inverse matrix to express \mathbf{x}, t in terms of \mathbf{x}, t .

$$\phi'' = kQ / \sqrt{x''^2 + y''^2 + z''^2} \quad ((10))$$

Thus, $\phi = g kQ / \sqrt{g^2(x-vt)(x-vt) + y^2 + z^2}$ ((11))

Given Newton's second law: d/dt momentum = forces, A should act as a momentum. If one wishes to use the Lagrangian formalism, momentum $(i) = dL/dv_i$. Thus, $v \cdot A$, but here v is the velocity of a moving particle influenced by E and B (i.e. by ϕ and A).

One may see the relativistic meaning of $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial.

Now $-v$ is the velocity of the moving frame.

E is a vector in x space and such a vector should contain g , we argue, even though the function of E may. One may see that:

$$-\text{grad } \phi = - (g(x-v''t) e_i + y e_j + x e_k) / (g(x-v''t)(x-v''t) + yy+xx)^{3/2} \quad ((12))$$

The vector piece contains g . In order to remove it, one requires a $-v v g(x-vt) e_i$ term. Here e_i, e_j, e_k are unit vectors in the x, y, z direction. This is exactly what $-dA/dt$ partial provides. Thus, $-dA/dt$ partial is added to $-\text{grad } \phi$ for special relativistic reasons.

Thus dA_i/dt full = dA_i/dt partial + $v_j d/dx_j A_i$, yields the piece dA/dt partial needed to combine with $-\text{grad } \phi$.

Given that $A=v'' \phi$, and that $\text{grad } \phi$ is related to a force, one should seek a force linked with grad and A together. Such a force should contribute a force along the y direction between a test charge q and Q . This leads to the form: $q v_x(\text{grad} \times A)$, where v is the velocity of the particle.

The Lagrangian approach is usually applied to a particle which may move freely with v and $A(r,t), \phi(r,t)$. When calculating the force on a test charge q , one may use v'' , the velocity of the moving charge Q and q , because both are seen from the frame moving with velocity $-v''$.

The point we wish to make is that even without a Lagrangian formalism, A is momentum vector, if one considers a charge at rest as seen from a frame moving with $-v''$.

We argue that it is the special relativistic form giving rise to A, ϕ , which leads to considerations of forces as seen from the moving frame. In other words, without a Lagrangian formalism, one may obtain: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial and $B = \text{grad} \times A$, such that $v \times B$ is the force for a charge moving with a velocity v , but $B(v'')$ and $E(v'')$. The Lagrangian approach preserves these special relativistic results, such that $-d v \cdot A / dx_i$ and $v \cdot \text{grad} A$ from $d/dt A$ yield $v \times B$. The fact that A appears as a momentum in the first place follows from special relativity.

In other words, the Lagrangian formalism may be seen to arise from the special relativistic considerations of A as a momentum and the effects of dA/dt as a force. Pieces are missing from dA/dt , namely $-\text{grad} (v \cdot A)$ and one may put these two ideas together and obtain the Lagrangian approach, at least for the electromagnetic example.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one may ask: How does the Lagrangian formalism arise? We argue that from special relativity, a potential $q\phi$ transforms like rest mass and gives rise to A , the electromagnetic potential. Thus, $d/dt A$ must represent a force. We show that $-dA/dt$ partial has relativistic relevance in combining with $-\text{grad } \phi$ to eliminate a factor $1/(1-vv/cc)$. The second part $-v \cdot \text{grad } A$ represents an arrangement of v , grad and A , but another type of arrangement is available, namely $-\text{grad}(v \cdot A)$. This leads to the notion of a Lagrangian function, namely momentum $= dL/dv$ such that $d/dt dL/dv$ yields pieces of force, but $-\text{grad } L$ yields other pieces of force.

References

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